

A mapping review of barriers and facilitators to a dementia diagnosis adopting an intersectionality lens: A protocol paper

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Introduction

Current global policy directives advocate an early or ‘timely diagnosis’ of dementia. Although, at present, there is limited longitudinal empirical evidence to draw on (Farina et al., 2020), research suggests that receiving a diagnosis of dementia in a timely fashion may help the individual and their family to: sustain well-being for longer (providing people psychological benefits and time to adjust to the diagnosis as well as facilitating access to services and drug treatments); better manage the condition (enabling people time to plan for the future and make decisions about financial and legal affairs whilst they still have capacity); and uphold their human rights (ensuring the person can fulfil their ‘right to know’ they have dementia) (ADI, 2011; Dubois, 2016).

Despite this, many people may not receive a formal diagnosis or, if they do, it is confirmed in the later stages of the condition (Alzheimer’s Europe, 2018; Lang et al., 2017). Unsurprisingly therefore, research over the past 30 years has sought to gather the perspectives of health professionals and/or people with dementia and their carers on differing aspects of the diagnostic process. Numerous reviews within this time have brought together this body of work with the aim of elucidating the barriers and facilitators to disclosing, receiving and managing a diagnosis (Bunn et al., 2012; Dubois et al., 2016; Parker et al., 2020; Poyser and Tickle, 2019). These reviews highlight barriers associated with clinical practice, including clinicians’ perceived lack of training in diagnosing and disclosing dementia, as well as people’s attitudes towards, and understandings of dementia and the services available to them. What is noteworthy about this work, however, is that researchers often treat people with dementia as a homogeneous population and only on occasions have certain intersections been explored within the diagnosis process. These include the context of rural living (Szymczynska et al., 2011), young onset dementia (O’Malley et al., 2019) and Black (Regan et al., 2013), minority ethnic (Kenning et al., 2017) and South Asian (Hossain et al., 2018) groups.

It is important that we develop a more nuanced understanding of the diagnosis process to determine whether certain barriers and facilitators are more pertinent for people depending on aspects of their social location (living context, age, gender, ethnicity, race etc) as well as understand how these determinants may intersect to influence people’s overall experiences of this process. It is also crucial to identify gaps in the literature where future research would be beneficial. This will enable us to better address the challenges that people may encounter when seeking a timely diagnosis for dementia.

Rationale

A recent systematic review has explored the barriers and facilitators to seeking help for a dementia diagnosis (Parker et al., 2020). However, when synthesising the studies, ethnicity was the only social categorization in which the authors discussed barriers and facilitators of a dementia diagnosis. As such, it is unclear the extent to which the literature explores different social categorisations and intersectionalities. We plan to run a mapping review of the literature, to identify evidence gaps (Schmucker et al., 2013), typical through the visual representation of data (Miake-Lye et al., 2016).

Methods

The adopted a similar systematic review methodology as Parker and colleagues adopted. Studies included the study were included in this mapping review and additional studies (2018 – Present) will be included.

Eligibility criteria

Criteria taken from Parker et al:

Inclusion Criteria

- Studies with an aim/research question (or questions asked during data collection) that relate to barriers or facilitators to help seeking for a dementia diagnosis.
- Findings from the perspective of carers or people subsequently diagnosed with any sub-type of dementia
- Carers who provide informal or formal care.

Exclusion Criteria

- Reporting only demographic characteristics in relation to help seeking
- Findings related to help seeking for care or support post-diagnosis
- Reporting barriers or facilitators after first contact with a health professional

Studies were not excluded on the basis of study design or outcome measure.

Information sources

All studies identified in the systematic review by Parker et al., were included. An updated literature search was conducted on PubMed, PsychINFO, CINAHL Complete, and SCOPUS. Only peer-review, primary data articles will be included, though we will use existing reviews and bibliographies to help identify any missed literature.

Search Strategy

We adapted the search terms identified by Parker et al. (2020). When piloting the search strategies, we ensured that the all the articles identified in Parker study were also identified in our search strategy, prior to limiting to studies published following 1st January 2018. Search terms can be split into four categories: 1) condition, 2) barriers/facilitators, 3) diagnosis, and 4) exclusion. See Table 1 for a summary.

Table 1. Example search strategies for two databases that will be used in mapping review.

Search no.	PubMed	PsychINFO
Complete search	(dement*[Title] OR Alzheimer*[Title] OR "lewy bod*[Title] OR "memory problem"[Title] OR "cognitive disorder*[Title] OR "neurocognitive disorder*[Title] OR confus*[Title] OR forgetful*[Title]) AND ("help seeking"[Title/Abstract] OR "help-seeking"[Title/Abstract] OR seek*[Title/Abstract] OR access*[Title/Abstract] OR delay*[Title/Abstract] OR avoid*[Title/Abstract] OR barrier*[Title/Abstract] OR facilitat*[Title/Abstract] OR enable*[Title/Abstract] OR trigger*[Title/Abstract] OR obstacle*[Title/Abstract]) AND (diagnosis[Title/Abstract] OR "early diagnosis"[Title/Abstract] OR delay* diagnosis[Title/Abstract] OR "late diagnosis"[Title/Abstract] OR undiagnosed[Title/Abstract] OR undetected[Title/Abstract]) NOT (Peptide OR in-vivo OR mouse OR mice OR MRI OR PET OR biomarkers OR animal OR gene OR genotype)	ti((dement* OR Alzheimer* OR ("lewy bodies" OR "lewy body") OR "memory problem" OR ("cognitive disorder" OR "cognitive disorders") OR "neurocognitive disorder*" OR confus* OR forgetful*)) AND ab(diagnosis OR "early diagnosis" OR delay* diagnosis OR "late diagnosis" OR undiagnosed OR undetected) AND ab(("help seeking" OR "help-seeking" OR seek*OR access* OR delay* OR avoid* OR barrier* OR facilitat* OR enable* OR trigger* OR obstacle*)) NOT (Peptide OR in-vivo OR mouse OR mice OR MRI OR PET OR biomarkers OR animal OR gene OR genotype)

Study records

Eligible peer review articles will be classed as the study record. Multiple eligible articles that are derived from the same sample will be grouped together as a single record.

Electronic search results will be downloaded into Mendeley™ (or equivalent) bibliographic software, where duplicates will be deleted. The de-duplicated list of a studies will then be uploaded to an web platform (<https://rayyan.qcri.org/>)(Ouzzani et al., 2016), which will allow for titles and abstracts to be screened by two researchers independently.

Study selection

A single reviewer will independently screen titles and abstracts for all records. Two reviewers (NF and BH) will each independently screen 10% of the study records to confirm eligibility. Any disagreement will be discussed and resolved as a team. As a secondary check, interrater reliability (Cohen's kappa) will be calculated between the lead reviewer and secondary reviewers' initial decisions. If the kappa statistic is below 0.80 then an additional

10% of the study records will be reviewed in duplicate. The involvement of the secondary reviewers will continue until this threshold is met, at which point the lead reviewer will continue reviewing the title and abstracts independently.

We will collect the full texts of all potentially eligible studies, which will then be reviewed in duplicate for eligibility.

We will use Cohen's kappa statistics to measure agreement between reviewers at both the screening and the full-text inclusion/exclusion step, and report reasons of exclusion as appropriate.

Data abstraction

Data, defined as any information about (or deriving from) a study record, will be extracted from the full texts by a single reviewer, and checked by the review team. All data will be extracted and entered into a pre-piloted form, for it to be synthesised in the mapping review. We will not extract data that are outside the scope of this mapping review (e.g., healthcare professionals).

Data items that are not reported or are unclear will be flagged as such. No efforts will be made to seek out this data from the original author.

Data items

- Study design
- Publication date
- Geographic location
- Barrier and facilitators for dementia diagnosis (as identified by the study's authors)
- Sample size
- Sample characteristics of participants (e.g. age, gender, ethnicity) – reported as averages (e.g. mean or median; standard deviations or interquartile ranges), or frequencies.
- Interpretative social categorisation – Explicit categorisation from authors about how their findings relate to a social categorisation (e.g. age, gender, ethnicity, sexuality), and whether intersectionality occurred.

Risk of bias

The focus of this mapping review is not to appraise the quality or risk of bias of included studies. Recent systematic reviews on the topic have comprehensively appraised some of the papers that will be included within this study (Parker et al., 2020).

Data Synthesis

In line with previous evidence mapping guidelines, the focus of this review was to visualise the findings. A series of figures will be used to highlight the number of studies that reported barriers of dementia over time, split by social categorisation. Social categorisations will be derived primarily using a bottom-up approach (i.e. based on social categories reported within

study records). We will adopt approaches similar to qualitative research in which researchers will independently “code” and group categories together. The exact terminology will be discussed and decided amongst the research team. A matrix will be developed, similar to that presented elsewhere (Anstee et al., 2011), highlighting the number of studies that have identified dementia diagnosis barriers split by social categorisation across one axis. The matrix will also indicate the study design of these studies.

Discussion

This study seeks to systematically update the literature surrounding barriers and facilitators of receiving a dementia diagnosis, building upon the review by Parker et al. (2020). In a novel component, we will adopt mapping review methodology to help us identify gaps in the literature in relation to exploring barriers and facilitators based on social categorisation.

We have used a pragmatic method of utilising the literature identified in a previous systematic review and then running a new search to identify more recent literature. Whilst not well defined, this could be classified as an “update” (Moher & Tsertsvadze, 2006). Such an approach has benefits of being more efficient on researcher time. Notably, the ultimate inclusion of studies from the previous review is dependent on the original accuracy, whilst the consistency of adhering to the inclusion in this “update” will be undefined.

References

- Alzheimer's Disease International (2011). *World Alzheimer Report 2011: The benefits of early diagnosis and intervention*. London. UK
- Alzheimer's Europe (2018). *European Carers' Report 2018: Carers' experiences of diagnosis in five European countries*. Alzheimer's Europe: Luxembourg
- Anstee, S., Price, A., Young, A., Barnard, K., Coates, B., Fraser, S., & Moran, R. (2011). Developing a matrix to identify and prioritise research recommendations in HIV Prevention. *BMC Public Health*, 11, 381. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-11-381>
- Bunn F, Goodman C, Sworn K, Rait G, Brayne C, Robinson L, et al. (2012) Psychosocial factors that shape patient and carer experiences of dementia diagnosis and treatment: a systematic review of qualitative studies. *PLoS Medicine*. 9:e1001331
- Dubois B, Padovani A, Scheltens P, Rossi A, Dell'Agnello G. (2016) Timely diagnosis for Alzheimer's disease: a literature review on benefits and challenges. *Journal of Alzheimer's disease*; 49:617-31
- Farina, N., Hicks, B., Baxter, K., Birks, Y., Brayne, C., Dangoor, M., et al. (2020). DETERMINants of quality of life, care and costs, and consequences of INequalities in people with Dementia and their carers (DETERMIND): A protocol paper. *International journal of geriatric psychiatry*, 35(3), 290-301.
- Hossain, M., Crossland, J., Stores, R., Dewey, A., & Hakak, Y. (2018). Awareness and understanding of dementia in South Asians: A synthesis of qualitative evidence. *Dementia*, 1471301218800641.
- Kenning, C., Daker-White, G., Blakemore, A., Panagioti, M., & Waheed, W. (2017). Barriers and facilitators in accessing dementia care by ethnic minority groups: a meta-synthesis of qualitative studies. *BMC psychiatry*, 17(1), 316.
- Lang L, Clifford A, Wei L, Zhang D, Leung D, Augustine G, et al. (2017). Prevalence and determinants of undetected dementia in the community: a systematic literature review and a meta-analysis. *BMJ Open*; 7:e011146
- Miake-Lye, I. M., Hempel, S., Shanman, R., & Shekelle, P. G. (2016). What is an evidence map? A systematic review of published evidence maps and their definitions, methods, and products. *Systematic Reviews*, 5(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-016-0204-x>
- Moher, D., & Tsertsvadze, A. (2006). Systematic reviews: When is an update an update? *The Lancet*, 367(9514), 881–883. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(06\)68358-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(06)68358-X)
- O'Malley, M., Carter, J., Stamou, V., LaFontaine, J., Oyeboode, J., & Parkes, J. (2019). Receiving a diagnosis of young onset dementia: a scoping review of lived experiences. *Aging & mental health*, 1-12.
- Ouzzani, M., Hammady, H., Fedorowicz, Z., & Elmagarmid, A. (2016). Rayyan—A web and mobile app for systematic reviews. *Systematic Reviews*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-016-0384-4>
- Parker, M., Barlow, S., Hoe, J., & Aitken, L. (2020). Persistent barriers and facilitators to seeking help for a dementia diagnosis: A systematic review of 30 years of the perspectives

of carers and people with dementia. *International Psychogeriatrics*, 1–24.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1041610219002229>

Poyser CA, and Tickle A. (2019) Exploring the experience of the disclosure of a dementia diagnosis from a clinician, patient and carer perspective: a systematic review and Meta-ethnographic synthesis. *Aging & mental health*. 23:1605-15

Regan, J. L. (2016). Ethnic minority, young onset, rare dementia type, depression: a case study of a Muslim male accessing UK dementia health and social care services. *Dementia*, 15(4), 702-720.

Schmucker, C., Motschall, E., Antes, G., & Meerpohl, J. J. (2013). Methoden des Evidence Mappings. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt - Gesundheitsforschung - Gesundheitsschutz*, 56(10), 1390–1397. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00103-013-1818-y>

Szymczynska, P., Innes, A., Mason, A., & Stark, C. (2011). A review of diagnostic process and postdiagnostic support for people with dementia in rural areas. *Journal of primary care & community health*, 2(4), 262-276.